

THE ROLE OF IDEOLOGICAL PROFILACTICS IN THE PROCESS OF IDEOLOGICAL UPBRINGING

Siddiqov Jamoldin Jalolovich

Director of the 2nd Vocational School of Bagdod District of Fergana region

Jaloliddinov Javlonbek Jamoldin o'g'li

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute 2nd year student

Annotation. In this article, the role and role of ideological profiling practices in increasing the effectiveness of the process of ideological upbringing of the young stratum of the population are analyzed.

Keywords. Ideological immunity, ideological profilactics, national idea, social institutions, political institutions, spirituality, national values, ideological and educational approaches.

The role of ideological profilactics in the formation of ideological immunity is on the floor. Ideological profilactics is the main factor shaping and developing ideological ideas and ideology, the ideological immune system of man. In its essence, it is a measure aimed at preventing the penetration of yacht ideas and eliminating them.[1] This means that ideological profilactics covers a set of ideological-educational, political, economic, social, spiritual works carried out by citizens, social institutions in various forms, the system of upbringing properly organized in this area.

The importance and necessity of ideological profilactics is explained by the fact that it provides for the prosperity, development of the nation, serves to unite all nationalities in the country, all citizens in one common goal. Therefore, it is important to teach the essence and significance of the National idea to all members of society, especially young people.[2]

Ideological profilactics covers a set of ideological-educational, political, economic, social, spiritual work carried out by citizens, social institutions in different forms. Ideological immunity on the basis of the National ideaitet every young man and girl, citizen relies on knowledge about the meaning and essence of

independence, the results of the reforms carried out in our country, the history of the world and the achievements of the Universal Civilization.[3] Ideological profilactics is manifested in the activity of man on the path of Vatan and people's interests. Ideological profiling requires free, independent thinking, respect for national and universal values, the transformation of humanism into everyday life activity.

The only goal and the main factor in the perfect implementation of these processes is determined by the formation, improvement of a sense of love and loyalty to the motherland.[4] In order to educate our children in the spirit of love for their homeland, our rich history, devotion to the holy religion of our fathers, we must first carry out ideological profilactic measures in them. Let our young people grow up as people who, at the same time, deeply understand the national identity of the world, take a step forward with the Times.

That is, both the “call” of ignorant fanatics and those ideas that reject the concepts of morality, completely alien to us, can not influence them.[5] In the protection of the younger generation from moral encroachments, the realization of indecent habits that are encountered in society and have a negative impact on its development from time immemorial, the elimination of them or the Prevention of unpleasant situations that they bring is a necessity of Bugun. After all, they are the vices that bring the nation and society into being.

Ideological profiling is divided into internal and external types according to the essence of its content. First of all, it is our duty to completely rid our society of such vices as selfishness and apathy, kinship and localism, cooperation and self-interest, and disregard for others.[6] It falls primarily on the part of the general public, especially intellectuals, scientists and writers, people of art and culture, people who devote themselves to the sphere of spirituality. The feeling of envy, which leaves a severe complication in the life of Man and society, first of all, arises as a result of a burn, constipation, instead of seeing others, rejoice in their achievement.[7] In particular, it is not surprising that in the Blessed hadiths it was said that “avoid being jealous of someone, because no matter how the fire ends up burning firewood, the reward that Envy also ends up burning your deeds in the same

way.” Our people have been open-minded, sincere and hardworking, highly valued. After all, the upbringing of such people is the main profilactic event for our society. This is the first appearance of internal profilactics.[8]

The establishment of social stability in society is an important condition of internal ideological profilactics. For the provision of social justice, it means the rule of law in the country, equality of citizens before the law and the implementation of their work activities within the framework of the law. Uzbekistan is a multinational state. Many nationalities and nationalities live in Uzbekistan. All conditions have been created for them. Ensuring the rights of members of society is also an important condition of ideological profilactics. As indicated in the Constitution of Uzbekistan, which is our main law, it is necessary to provide socio-political, economic and legal basis for full implementation.[9] The belief that independence is the right in our people serves as the basis for all spheres of social life. One of the most important principles is to go along the way of raising the standard of living of all categories of members of society and increase its well-being. In this regard, the aspiration of the state to improve the lifestyle of all strata of society is an important condition of internal profilactics.[10]

The external form of ideological prfilactics. It is necessary to work with the countries of the world and the region on the principles of equal partnership, peace and friendship. Bunda is important in the struggle for mutual socio-political relations, stable peace and the construction of a democratic, just society.[11] The peace, stability, tranquility and creative work environment established for citizens in the country is one of the important conditions that is firmly established. Stability, peace, harmony - these are important preventive measures of our statehood.

One of the important conditions for ensuring socio-political stability is the re-arming and renewal of the Armed Forces, Defense power in the military and technical aspects in order to ensure peace and tranquility in the country, increasing the capacity of our national army.[12] In this regard, strengthening relations with developed countries in political, socio-economic and especially military spheres is one of the principles of great importance in order to protect and strengthen the

borders of our country. Equal economic, political, cultural cooperation with the world community is an important condition of external profilactics.[13]

At the same time, the formation and improvement of our national culture in the minds of citizens is also a sign of ideological profiling. In particular, the annual national cultural events in the capital and the regions in the promotion of national traditions and culture can be a clear proof of our above views.[14] Many such prestigious events have been held, through which special attention is paid to popularization of our national culture at the national and international level, preserving our national heritage, restoring ancient traditions in the direction of Applied Art and craftsmanship.[15] In particular, the holding of various festivities, contests, national art fairs, exhibitions, concerts is a clear evidence of this.

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